

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B257
 Date: 15 January 2007
 Take Off 09:03:10 15:19:17
 Landing: 14:17:47 16:04:17
 Flight Time 5h18m14 0h45m00

Campaign: WINTEX – CAESAR

Operating Area: N Sea. Refuel at Newcastle

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	DFL
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	DFL
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	DFL
4	Mission Scientist	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	AVAPS training	Bob Wells	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2 / ARIES	Stuart Newman	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	MARSS / DEIMOS 1	Jeff Brown	Met Office
11	TAFTS 1	Paul Green	Imperial College
12	TAFTS 2	Neil Humpage	Imperial College
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Flight Track:

B257 Track 15-JAN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B257

Date: 15/10/07

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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083957		event	0.09 kft	125	INU to Nav
085510		event	0.09 kft	126	start taxi
090310		T/O	1.6 kft	295	Cranfield
090748		event	7.0 kft	045	Nev zero
090855		event	7.0 kft	020	JW zero
091656		event	13.0 kft	357	Heimann cal over cloud field
093042		event	13.0 kft	336	JW zero
094106		event	13.0 kft	046	TWC started working
095140		Video	4.7 kft	048	start FFC UFC/DFC
095553	100557	Run 1	0.12 - 0.18 kft	029	100ft
095553		event			Heimann cal.
100558	101030	Profile 1	0.18 - 4.0 kft	031	
101207	102838	Profile 1	4.0 - 20.0 kft	221	
103108	103331	Profile 1	20.0 - 22.1 kft	033	
103413	103523	Profile 2	22.0 - 21.0 kft	029	
103853	104853	Run 2.1	21.0 kft	180	
104359		event	21.1 kft	179	103500 P0 iced?
105050	110056	Run 3.1	20.0 kft	352	
110239	110404	Orbit 1.1	20.1 - 19.9 kft	278	50 deg
110439	110558	Orbit 1.2	20.2 - 20.1 kft	238	60 deg
110722	111408	Profile 3	20.0 - 27.0 kft	181	
111043		event	23.8 kft	178	upper BBR reset
111623	112626	Run 4.1	27.0 kft	350	
112736	112943	Profile 4	27.2 - 29.0 kft	330	
113142	114140	Run 5.1	29.0 - 32.0 kft	183	
114345	114609	Profile 5	32.0 kft	359	
114700	114807	Profile 5	32.0 kft	000	
114807	115313	Run 6.1	32.0 kft	359	
115520	120720	Run 6.2	32.0 kft	358	
115616		Sonde 1	32.0 kft	358	
120110		Sonde 2	32.0 kft	357	
120620		Sonde 3	32.0 kft	357	
120937	122000	Run 6.3	32.0 kft	357	
122115	122408	Profile 6	32.2 - 34.0 kft	326	
122617	123616	Run 7.1	34.1 - 34.0 kft	181	

123616	123952	Profile 7	34.0 - 31.1 kft	177
124156	124235	Run 8.1	31.1 - 31.0 kft	351
124236	124357	Profile 8	31.0 - 30.0 kft	359
124357	125350	Run 9.1	30.0 kft	359
125547	130601	Run 9.2	30.1 - 29.9 kft	192
130601	130702	Profile 9	29.9 - 29.1 kft	187
130903	131051	Orbit 2.1	29.1 - 29.0 kft	223
131124	131326	Orbit 2.2	29.1 - 29.0 kft	278
131352	131530	Profile 10	29.0 - 28.0 kft	319
131531	132529	Run 10.1	28.0 kft	333
141747		Land	0.42 kft	194 Newcastle
142333		event	0.42 kft	194 final posn 55 02.00N 01 41.93W

B257 Track 15-JAN-07

CAESAR Sortie Brief

Radiative properties of cirrus

B257 15/01/07

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to determine the radiative properties of frontal cirrus using multiple frequencies from the range of remote sensing instruments on the aircraft. For closure it is also important to determine the in-situ properties of the cloud and to make radiative measurements of the atmosphere above and below the cirrus. To obtain in-situ vertical distributions either perform profile ascents and descents, or a Lagrangian spiral descent if the cirrus is extensive and homogenous. Measurements should be made advecting with the wind, such that the same airmass is continuously measured.

Straight and level runs should be made below, above and in the cirrus. A 100ft run over the sea will be required to measure the SST. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

Satellite overpass 12:01

Weather conditions:

Frontal cirrus. Clear sky below the cirrus in the measurement area is essential. Ideally the cirrus should not extend above 35,000ft.

Locations:

North Sea.

Clearances:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes and runs at 100ft.

Instruments required:

Critical: ARIES, SWS, SID1, 2DC, Temp, Humidity, AVAPS

Desirable: MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, CPI, SID2, FFSSP, 2DP, CIPs, Heimann, Core chem (auto mode OK)

B257 15/01/07

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	0900	Takeoff from Cranfield & transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	45	45
2	0945	Straight and level run of 10 mins duration at 100 ft over sea only. (Missed out for Chilbolton location).	10	55
3	0955	Profile ascent from min altitude to 1000ft below cirrus base at 1000ft/min (interrupted when necessary)	35	90
4	1030	Fly 3 straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft below cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins.	35	125
5	1105	Fly two orbits below cloud at SZA (or max) banking angle	10	135
6	1115	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus base	5	140
7	1120	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	150
8	1130	Profile ascent to 1000ft below cirrus top	10	160
9	1140	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	170
10	1150	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus top	5	175
11	1155	Fly three straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop between 1 and 3 sondes during one run, ideally during satellite overpass	35	210
12	1201	Satellite overpass		
13	1230	EITHER Perform a Lagrangian spiral descent at 2 ms ⁻¹ , advecting with the wind, to 1000ft below cirrus base, then go to 16	25	235
13	1230	OR Profile descent to level approx. half way between cloud top and base	5	215
14	1235	Fly 1 or 2 straight and level runs 1000ft in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	225
15	1245	Profile descent to 1000ft below cloud base	10	235
16	1255	Fly one straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus base, orientated across wind, of 10 mins.	10	245
17	1305	Perform one orbit at SZA (or max) banking angle	5	250
18	1310	Profile descent to transit altitude	10	260
19	1320	Transit to Cranfield	45	305
20	1405	Land		

AQUA 2007/01/15 AQUA ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/01/03
 ■ lat: 51.57 slon: 358.69 AIRS swath angle: 47.3 deg res: 9 km

Instrument operator instructions:

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction as each other (except during cal). ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft)
- However, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 mins of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time

ARIES

- If it is still unstable for zenith views (shutter open) at high altitudes, it is better to get 30 secs of good data in a 10 min run (with rest of time with shutter closed viewing calcs or nadir) than all bad data – let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Zenith = 6 deg forward

Phil Brown

15 Jan 2007

IR satellite images just prior to takeoff show plenty of cirrus to the south of frontal zone, in N.Sea. This appeared to have strong orographic influence with a semi-stationary edge just off the E.Coast. Hence flight legs could be arranged on more fixed ground positions.

During transit over Lincs/E.Yorks extensive stratocumulus over the land but could see breaks out over the N.Sea. Descent to 100ft in a region where the cloud was breaking up then did 100ft leg alongwind. 18-20 m/s surface wind with lots of whitecapping on the sea surface. Thick cirrus bands were present above, sufficient to obscure sun.

Profile ascent to 22000ft which was just into cloud. Descend to FL210 for first run. Managed to find a slot where 10min leg was over an area free of low cloud but just into cloud. Further leg at FL200 to be more below cloud. Following this, 2 orbits at about 55 deg bank. Value of these may not be too high as sun was pretty much obscured by the thick Ci. Further legs at 27000 and 29000 within the cloud layer.

Ascent to FL320 to do a short 5min leg, then turn reciprocal to do 12 min leg at the satellite overpass time 1201. 3 sondes on this leg 1min after start and then 5min intervals. Cloud seemingly thicker at N end of legs. Further 10 min Northbound leg at 32000 and then South at 34000. This leg seemed to be above most of the Ci although there were still some occasional bits of cloud around and above flight level.

Descent to 30000 feet for southbound leg. Two 50deg orbits at S end where the Ci was thinner. These orbits were pretty much below cloud although there was by now more low cloud encroaching below. Final leg at FL280 which started out below Ci and ended up just above the cloud base.

As usual, the cirrus was by no means a uniform level layer. Generally tended to be thicker and with lower base altitude towards the north and thinner, higher base towards the south. Lower cloud was thinnest or absent below the thickest Ci regions. Gives the impression that Sc was being dissipated by the decreased cloud top cooling beneath the thick cirrus.

Overall, the flight achieved some legs that were clearly below the CI, some at a variety of altitudes within it and one that was almost but not quite at the Ci top. Unfortunately, we were still somewhat within the cloud at overpass time although downwelling views were taken and sondes dropped at this time.

Turbulence probe centre port was unresponsive for most of the time at high level. Looks like icing although never in any wet cloud.

General synoptic situation.

Frontal system to the N with strong westerly warm sector flow over UK.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date 15/1/07 Name P. Brown Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0901				dog mine	T/O airfield
—		4000ft			cloudbase, 8/8
—		5150			top.
0935		13000		57 24 -0 18	Sc breaking below e to N, with some wave fx.
—		"	046		now heading NE, cloud appears to breakup ahead. Thick Ci band overhead.
0952		4000 ↓			Few patches of Sc, big. in wave crests.
0954					Strong sc wind - lots of white capping.
095553		100	027		Start R1 +10min.
—					Seems free of low clouds
—					Thick Ci above
0958				56.00 1.24	+8 Heinmann.
			030		210/18 ms ⁻¹
100558					End R1 / Start P1.
100830		2500 ↑			Some
		4000			hold P1 e reverse.
					Patches of Sc around during turn.
1021		12000	217		low cloud free on L side of track to the SE.
103341		22000			End P1 into cloudbase
103523		21000			End P2
103853		"	180		Start R2 270/26.
					DFC video on.
1035					Centre port frozen on to b. patche.
—					

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date 15/1/07 Name Phil Brown Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10416	2	21000	180		Just about going to make 10 min cloud (near) below.
/					sent little patches to the W of track.
/					ci base rises as we come South.
104853					End R2
105050		20000	356		Start R3
/					Centre port responding again.
/					Doesn't look like icing.
		20000			End R3.
					Start 01.1 50deg.
10558					End 01.2 60deg.
					Thick Ci above throughout.
10722		20000	182	56 12.0 2 30.0	P3
/		24000			In cloud.
11408		27000			End P3 then turn N.
11623		"	360		R4.1
11000		"			Turb probe P0 funny again.
		"			low cloud not visible, N end of leg may encroach into area where low cloud was.
/					P0 -3.5 hPa
					ci thicker at N end of track.
112624		27000			End R4.1
			330	56 48.0 02 48.0	Start P4
113142		29000	182	56 48.0 2 30.0	Start R5.1 sun visible.
/					Turb P0 still screwy
1136					contour. -49 / -49.76

T Td.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date 15/1/07 Name P. Brown Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	5.1	29000			End 5.1
1144		1			Start P5
114609		31000			hold ?
1148-		32000	340		Start 6.1 5 min leg.
—					Contract. -56.74 / -56.73
115314		"			End 6.1
115520					Start 6.2 12 min
115616					Sonde 1 all good
1201					Sonde 2 all good.
120616					Sonde 3. Ci getting thicker again.
—					Pass that there might be a layer above at this end.
					thicker
					End 6.2 Spc visible during turn.
121356					Start 6.3 No Sp.
122617		34000	180		Start 7.1 Certainly v. close to cloud top but not quite.
123616		"	180	56 12.0 2 52.0	End 7.1 / P7
123952		31000			hold P7, Patchy Sc to the right
124155		"			Start 8.1
124236					End 8.1 for FL300.
124357		30000	360		Start 9.1 sort of below cloud at S end but thicker as go N.
1248					Spc. no longer visible.
125350					End 9.1. 2 reciprocal.
125547					Start 9.2 Spc just visible

300
300
250 orbits

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date **15/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **4**

(MISSION SCI 2)

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0900		0		Granfield	Take off
0905		FL050			Stratocumulus 7/8 base at 4000ft, top at 5000ft
0940		FL130		Transit over N-sea	Sc much more broken here Cirrus above, reasonably thick
				54.5N 0E	upper pyrometer risen to 240W.m ⁻² No mid-level cloud then 330W.m ⁻²
0948		FL130			starting descent into area. preferring the eastmost extreme of the region to avoid patches of marine stratus.
					Cirrus seems quite extensive and located where forecast
09553	R1	100ft	30		SST ~ 8°C
100558	End R1	100ft	30		BL top ~ 5000ft
100558	Start P1	100ft	30		cirrus 54.5N - 56.5N
103331	End P1	FL220			
103413	Start P2	FL220			
103523	End P2	F210			Run just below cirrus base
103853	R2.1	FL210			Run just below cirrus, but 2D-C still showing low-medium concentrations
104853	End	FL210			
105050	R2.2	FL200			Descend to get clearly below cirrus Problem with ^{upper} pyrometer
	R3.1				
110056	End R2.2				
110250		FL200	01		ORBIT 1 @ 50° bank
110404			02		ORBIT 2 @ 60° bank

110558

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date **15/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1109					
110722	P3	FL200	180	SG-1 2.5E	Climbing up through cirrus 2D-C concentrations quite variable
111408	End P3	FL270	180		Seem to be about half way through cloud, maybe more.
111623	R4.1	FL270	355		No turbulence in the cirrus
					Cirrus seems to have higher top further north and lower base too.
112626	End R4.1	FL270	355		Run mid-way in cloud
113142	RS.1	FL290	180		Run hopefully ~1000ft below cloud top, but perhaps we are further below cloud top than 1000ft
					Aircraft max alt FL300 310
113500		FL290			Looks like we are contrailing again though not that easy to see because we are still within cloud.
114140	End RS.1	FL290	180		
114400		Clearly	Can	see we are	Contrailing again.
114700		FL310			Climbing up to FL 320
114807		FL320			
114807	R6.1	FL320	330		Still not quite above the cloud but it's quite bright so much optical depth above.
					Captain guesses cloud top could be around FL350. FL320 is current max altitude.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.257** Date **15/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11 5317	End R6.1	FL320	330	57.2.4E	
11 5520	R6.2	FL320	180	-	2nd SLR at max altitude
11 5620	Sonde 1	FL320	180	56.5.2.5E	Sonde 1 gone
12 01 30	Sonde 2	FL320	180		Sonde 2 gone
12 06 30	Sonde 3	FL320	180	55.9.2.6E	Sonde 3 gone
12 07	End R6.2	71'	"	55.8.2.7E	
12 09	R6.3	"	0	55.9.2.6E	3rd SLR at max altitude
12 10 00	"	"			Sonde 1 successful, splash down at surface
12 11 00	"	"	0		Still not above cloud
12 21	End R6.3		0		
12 21	R6		330		Climb to FL340, hoping to clear above cloud top
12 24 08	End PG	FL340	330	57.3.2.5E	Still not above the cirrus
12 26 17	R7.1	FL340	180	57.2.2.5E	Still contrailing (250 mb)
12 34	"	"	"		Come above cloud now
12 36 16	End R7.1				but still contrailing.
12 36 16 12 37 00	R7	FL320		56.2 N 3 E	Can see ground, cloud must be thin and/or have higher base here.
12 39 52	End P7	FL300			
12 41 56	R8.1	FL310	350		Air traffic prevents descent temporarily
12 43 57	R9.1	FL300	355	56.2 N 2.9 E	
12 53 50	End R9.1	"	"	57.1 3.1E	Can still see ground all along this run, must be much thinner than earlier in the flight.
12 55 47	R9.2	"	190		
13 0	End R9.2	"	190		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B257

Date: 15 Jan 07

Operator: JC

Page 1 of 1

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:02:00											FFSSP working SID1 Working (F drive, had to clear space) CIP A sampling & recording but probably not working PCASP working 2DC working 2DP working SID2 working
10:23:00	0		6	2	0					noisy	
103720			9	100	40	300	graupel				
103853	20	0.14	10	100	100	300	graupel				Start run 2.1
104300	10	0.17	13	100	10		Small ice			noisy	Rearm 2 1 command to reduce 2DP sampling
104600	12	0.13	14	10	12	400	Small ice			noisy	Descending to fl 200 FFSSP -5V @ -4.7
105100	11	0.13	15	0	1					noisy	Below cloud layer run 3.1
105300	6	0.12	15	0	0					noisy	Clear air
105500	5	0.11	15	0	0					noisy	Clear air
105900	11	0.09	15	5	0					noisy	Clear air
110200											Orbits
110700											Start of profile 3
110820	3	0.22	16	100	77	400	Small ice			Noisy	Into ice fl 215
111000	5	0.13	18	100	65	300	Small ice			Noisy	
111200											

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B257

Date: 15 Jan 07

Operator: JC

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
111200	4	0.13	21	200	350	200	Small ice			noisy	
111400	10	0.32	23	500	189	125	Small ice			Noisy	
111622											Run 4.1 fl270
111700	30	0.3	32	100	38	175	Small ice				
112000	6	0.3	37	100	63	150	Small ice				
112600	16	10	46	200	300	300	Small ice				End run
112400											2DP noise change
113200											Run 5.1 fl 290
113300	8	0.36	61	500	200	300	Small ice			Noise	
											2DP off to reduce noise data
113600	5	0.3	67	100	50	150	Small ice			Off	
113800	11	0.3	68	100	120	200	Small ice			Off	
114000	12	0.3	69	100	200	250	Small ice			Off	
114142											End run
114814											Run 6.1 fl 320
114900	14	0.16	81	100	40	180	Small ice				
115100	10	0.1	83	100	62	225	Small ice				
115500											Run 6.2 fl 320
115700	30	0.12	85	100	70	175	Small ice				
115900	45	0.15	86	100	20	150	Small ice				
120200	65	0.09	88	300	34	150	Small ice				
120400	75	0.06	91	200	31	120	Small ice				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B257

Date: 15 Jan 07

Operator: JC

Page 3 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
120600	100	0.07	92	100	0	0					
120720											End run
120940											Run 6.3
121200	170	0.06	95	100	20	150	Small ice				
121400	160	0.07	97	200	27	125	Small ice				
121600	200	0.07	99	100	41	200	Small ice				
121800	250	0.07	101	100	100	175	Small ice				
122000	250	0.07	101	100	40	200	Small ice				End run
											Run 7.1 fl340
122500			104	200							Occasional small ice, noise
122800			106	100							Occasional small ice, noise
123000			107	80							Noise, occasional small ice
123200			109	30							Noise, Occasional small ice
123400											Clear of cloud
123600											Clear of cloud
											End run, start profile
123800			100	200							Fl 320, some small ice, surface visible, thin cirrus below
124200											Run 8.1 fl310
											End run
124400											Run 9.1 fl 300
124500		noise	113	100	80	200	Small ice				
124700		noise	115	1000	40	175	Small ice				Cloud thickening surface not visible
124900		noise	118	300	70	200	Small ice				
125100		noise	119	100	46	175	Small ice				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B257

Date: 15 Jan 07

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Page 4 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
125300		noise	119	100	16	300	4				Bullet rosettes
125400											End run
125547											Start run 9.2
		OFF									PCASP ref volts cycling between 8 & 0 - switched off
125800			123	100	120	250	Small ice				
130000			124	100	100	200	Small ice				
130200			126	100	50	175	Small ice				
130400			126	70	70	125	Small ice				
130600			126	100	50	150	Small ice				
											End run
130630											Start profile
130800			127	70	40	150					Noise, occasional small ice Orbits
131531											
											Run 10.1 fl 280
131600			131	10	0	0					Clear air
131800			131	10	0	0					
132000			132	100	60	200	Small ice				
132200			133	100	35	250	Small ice				
132400			134	10	8	200	Small ice				
											End run

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B257 **T/O:** 09:03:10
Date of flight: 15/01/07 **Land:** 14:17:47

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B257
Date of Flight: 15/01/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	32762 blocks
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat = 279232
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 54033 Blocks written = 54033 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 090000 End = 142000dir Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2DP noisy throughout. Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 103000 End = 140000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	Y	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X =
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		Start = 103000 End = 140000 Time data processed to = 134507.9 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, ' PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT ', ' PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D ' ii). exit		Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =14920, 178
11) FLOODS> MODIFY	Y	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		X = A Y = (X+1) = B
12) CHECKS: Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>	Y	Correlated? Reasonable

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B257
Date of Flight: 15/01/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 090500 134500
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Merged OK? Y

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B257** Date **15/01/07** Operat or(s) **Aw** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0800						PREFLIGHT OK. NO MIR MODULES PRESENT FOR SWS, USHIMOR LSHIM.			
090300	Transit	FL050	174°	350	✓	take off Cranfield.			
						SWS vis module is 1003			
092630		FL130	174	350		DARK ALL at 350 int each			
092710		---		350		Scene all ---			
0940			6° Forward	350		SWS changed to Zenith view.			
094530						USH set to 500ms + Darked LSH " 750ms + Zeroed.			
095030						DARK ALL			
095040						Scene all.			
095420			175°	1000ms		Dark all at 1000ms.			
095445						Scene all. Bumpy!!			
095553	R1	100ft	175°	1000	✓	start R1 @ 100ft.			
100416			5° F	500		change view + DARK ALL			
100330		100ft.	5° F	500		Scene measure. ALL			
100558	R1 / P1	100ft →	5° F	500	✓	end R1 / START P1 TO CIRKUS base			
102000			"	500		DARK ALL			
102028		FL120	5° F	500		SCENE ALL	✓	✓	✓
102126						USHIM TO 750MS + DARK		✓	
102143						USH TO SCENE		✓	
102750		FL200		350		SWS TO 350MS + DARK			
102805						SWS SCENE	✓		
103331	P1	220	6° F	350		end P1 @ FL220			
103413	P2	220	---	---		start P2 @ FL220			
103523	P2	210				end P2			
103853	R2.1	210	6° F	350		Start R2.1. INT TIMES USH 750 LSH 1000			
104840						UP SHIM TO 400MS + DARK			
104905						USH SCENE			
104853	R2.1	FL200	6° F	350	✓	end R2.1.			
105050	R3.1	200	6° F	350		Start R3.1. USH 400ms LSH 1000ms			
110056	R3.1	200	6° F	350		end R3.1.			
110237	ORBIT 1.1	200	6° F	350		start orbit 1.1 @ 50° AOB			
110404						end orbit 1.1 GOOD!			
110439	ORBIT 1.2	200	6° F			start orbit 1.2 @ 60° AOB			
110558						end 1.2. GOOD!			
110722	P3	FL200 →				start P3			
111030						DARK ALL	✓	✓	✓
111057						SCENE ALL	✓	✓	✓
111510		FL270	6° F	250		SWS TO 250MS + DARK			
111521	P3	270				SWS SCENE MEASURE			
111623	R4.1	FL270	6° F	250		START R4.1. INT TIMES USH 400 LSH 1000			
112400		FL270	174° AFT			SWS TO NADIR FOR 2 mins			
112500			174° A	400		SWS TO 400 + DARK			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 257** Date **15/1/07** Operat or(s) **Aw** log page **2** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
112505	R4.1	270	174°A	400	-	SWS SCENE.			
112626	R4.1	270				end R4.1			
112736	P4	270	174°A	400		Start P4			
113142	R5.1	R290	6°F 50F	400		Start R5.1. SCAN HEAD V.V. STIFF!			
113200		290	6°F			Scan Head to 6°F. I'M SWEATING BUCKETS!			
113745	R5.1	290	6°F	250		SWS TO 250ms + DARK			
113755			6°F	250		SWS measure			
114140	R5.1	290	6°F	250		end R5.1			
						SWS HEAD FROZEN & V HARD TO MOVE AT THIS POINT.			
114345	PS	290							
114630		310	174°A	250		SWS TO NADIR!	✓		
114753		320	174°A	400		SWS TO 400ms + DARK	✓		
114801		320	174°A	400		SWS TO SCENE.	✓		
115140						LSH TO 750ms + DARK			✓
115204						LSH TO SCENE			✓
115353						UPSH TO 300ms + DARK		✓	
115405						USH TO SCENE		✓	
115501		320	174°A	350		SWS TO 350ms + DARK	✓		
115510		320	174°A	350		SWS SCENE	✓		
120720	R6.2	320	174°A	350		and R6.2			
120950	R6.3	320				Start R6.3			
122000	R6.3	320	174°A	350		and R6.3			
122127	R6	320	174°A			Start R6 to R340			
122234						DARK ALL	✓	✓	✓
122250						SCENE ALL	✓	✓	✓
122300				350		INT TIMES USH300 LSH750			
122408	R6	340	174°A			END R6 @ R340			
122455						USH TO 150ms + DARK		✓	
122458						USH TO SCENE		✓	
122617	R7.1	340	174°A	350		Start R7.1. SWS NADIR.			
122743						USH TO 300ms + DARK		✓	
122749						USH SCENE		✓	
123208		340	6°F	350		SWS TO ZENITH			
123253		340	6°F	500		SWS TO 500ms + DARK			
123300		340	6°F	500		SWS SCENE.			
123430		340				JUST ABOVE Ci.			
123600						INT TIMES USH300 LSH750			
123616	R7.1/P7	340	6°F	500		end R7.1 / start P7			
123752	P7	300	6°F	500		and P7.			
4113				350		SWS TO 350ms + DARK	✓		
4128						SWS SCENE	✓		
4140						LSH TO 500ms + DARK			✓
4154						LSH SCENE			✓
124156	R8.1	310	6°F	350		Start			
124236	R8.1/P8					end R8.1 / start P8			
124357	en R8 / R9.1	300	6°F	350		and P8 / start R9.1 SWS ZENITH			
125350	R9.1	300		350		and R9.1			
125450		300.	174°A	350		SWS TO NADIR FOR RECIPROCAL RUN.			
125547	R9.2	300				Start R9.2			
125630						DARK ALL			
125640						SCENE ALL			
130500						Reposition SWS TO ZENITH FOR ORBITS.			

IN CIRCLES OF VARYING THICKNESS
JUST ABOVE Ci.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B257

page 1 of 5

Date: 15/1/07

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA CAESAR FLIGHT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
075942		1x60	C	C	71.8	30.9	GROUND TESTS
080020		1x60	H	C	71.0	31.0	
080101		60x1	N	C	71.1	30.9	(the pan)
080203		60x1	Z	0	70.9	30.9	(overcast)
080246		1x60	C	1/2	71.1	30.8	
080320		1x60	H	C	71.0	30.9	
084852		1x60	C	C	70.7	31.2	
084941		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.9	
085021		60x1	N	C	71.0	30.9	(the pan)
085059		60x1	Z	0	71.7	31.0	(overcast)
085138		1x60	C	C	71.1	31.0	
085234		1x60	H	C	71.0	30.8	
<hr/>							
090314	TAKE-OFF						
090747		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.8	IN TRANSIT
090821		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.9	
090926		120x1	N	C	70.9	30.7	Above Sc
091039		120x1	Z	0	70.4	30.9	Wispy Ci above, thin
091148		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.8	
091220		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.8	
	DRS	091730	=				ARIES CLOCK 091736
094034		1x60	C	C	0.0	0.0	← software not responding
094135		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.4	
095602	100'	1x60	C	C	70.6	30.3	
5638	"	1x60	H	C			
5720	"	480 480x1	N	C			over ocean, overcast above
100121		1x60	C	C			
100258		1x60	H	C			
↓		120x1	Z	0			fairly uniform above by eye
100410		1x60	C	C			

ARIES flight log

Flight: B2S7

page 2 of 5

Date: 15/1/07 Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA CAESAR FLIGHT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 0446	100'	1x60	H	C			
10 0537		120x1	Z	0			End of run, into climb 100606
10 3901	R2.1 FL210	1x60	C	C	70.7	30.6	
10 3936	"	1x60	H	C	70.8	31.0	
10 4017	"	120x1	Z	0	70.1	29.8	Fairly uniform Ci above (report of just in base of cloud, 2D)
10 4129		1x60	C	C			
10 4204		1x60	H	C	70.7	31.2	
10 4248		240x1	Z	0	70.4	30.6	Uniform, looks thick above, clear below
10 4454		1x60	C	C	70.4	30.7	Note no "rest" period after zenith
10 4547		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.6	
10 4628		120x1	Z	0	70.3	30.4	Same conditions
10 4743		1x30	C	C	70.8	30.8	} short pause before; shorter sequences as test
10 4802	R3.1 R2.2	1x30	H	C	70.6	30.9	
10 5106	FL200	1x60	C	C	71.0	30.6	
10 5139		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.5	
10 5216		120x1	Z	0	69.7	30.3	No 2D evidence of cloud particles, so should be below cloud base now
10 5424		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.5	1 min. idle time before
10 5459		1x60	H	C			
10 5549		360x1	Z	0	70.0	30.4	Thickish, uniform above, clear below
10 5900		1x60	C	C	70.4	30.4	
10 5938		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.3	
11 0044		120x1	Z	0	69.8	30.4	End of run 110100
11 0154		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.0	Below-base runs finished early, so no time for nadir data now
11 0232		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.6	
11 0307	01.1	60x1	Z	0	70.0	30.6	
11 0354		1x60	C	C	71.1	30.5	
11 0428		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.4	
11 0505	01.2	120x1	Z	0	70.3	30.1	
11 0616		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.7	
11 0653		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.6	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B2S7

page 3 of 5

Date: 15/1/07

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA CAESAR FLIGHT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1116	R4.1	AT FL 270					IN CLOUD
	F290						
113145	RS.1	1x60	C	C			
113217		1x60	H	C	70.4	30.5	Still in cloud
113303		120x1	N	C	70.6	30.5	" (nadir - 5°?) — possible mistake
113431		120x1	N	C	70.7	30.6	true nadir (0°)
113543		1x60	C	C	70.4	30.4	
113624		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.4	(in cloud)
114905	FL 320 R6.1	1x60	C	C	70.6	31.1	In tops (but only just)
114938		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.4	
115026		120x1	N	C	70.6	30.2	sky visible above, but not above all of Ci
115138		1x60	C	C	70.4	30.4	
115226		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.3	
115423		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.5	
115459		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.4	
115536	R6.2 FL 320	240x1	N	C	70.6	30.8	more above now, still in tops
115747		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.5	
115825		1x60	H	C	70.5	31.1	
115905		480x1	N	C	70.5	30.1	Thin, wispy Ci above, but we are above most of it at least
120310		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.0	
120407		1x60	H	C	70.8	31.0	
120448		240x1	N	C	70.3	30.5	More above, we aren't close to being above it
120659		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.3	↳ thinner below toward end, sea visible
120735		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.5	(in turn)
120947		1x60	C	C	70.6		
121030		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.4	
121107	R6.3	360x1	N	C	70.2	30.6	
121413	FL 320	1x60	C	C	70.4	30.1	
121447		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.7	
121832		120x1	N	C	70.1	30.2	still in cloud
121946		1x60	C	C	70.5	30.5	(end of run)

ARIES flight log

Flight: B2S7

page 4 of 5

Date: 15/1/07

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA CAESAR FLIGHT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
122021		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.1	(turning)
122606	FL340	1x60	C	C			
122642	R7.1	1x60	H	C			
122724		210x1	N	C			Above a lot of it, but still not above all
		1x60	C				
		1x60	H				
122920		210x1	N	C	70.6	30.6	
123113		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.4	
123154		1x60	H	C			SWs stiff, but just moveable
123301		210x1	Z	O	70.1	30.0	View up for completion, not much above, particularly at end
123458		1x60	C	o/c	69.5	30.7	
123526		1x60	H	C	70.4	30.5	
124407	R9.1 FL300	1x60	C	C	70.5	31.0	
124443		1x60	H	C	70.2	31.3	In cloud
130735	FL290	1x60	C	C	70.5	30.4	Actually below cloud here
130807		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.2	
130850	02.1	120x1	Z	O			includes orbit
131005		1x60	C	C	70.3	30.0	
131037		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.1	
131153	0.2.2	240x1	Z	O	69.6	30.4	below cloud, mostly clear below includes roll-out of orbit at end
131358		1x60	C	C			Profile descent
131432		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.7	
131539	R10.1 FL280	1x60	C	C	70.3	30.5	
131614		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.3	* 60x1 by mistake? *
131710		240x1	Z	O	70.1	30.4	Some Cu below; mainly below Ci
131918		1x60	C	o/c	69.9	30.6	
132025		1x60	H	C	70.6	31.2	Now in cloud
132310		1x60	C	C			
132351		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.4	
132430		120x1	Z	O	70.4	29.7	In base unfortunately, sea vis. below
132534		120x1	N	C			End run (132541) (end of science) so only first few will be useable

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	15/01/07	Flight	B257	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Brown	Campaign	WINTEX			
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection					
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					
FERA on			at time		08:13:17
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	22°C	Ch	23°C	Ch18 20°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time		08:14:05
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290	Cold		290
Target heating					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time		08:18:08
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers					
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual
Weather	Cloud		Precip		
	Surface		Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$		at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start					
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again				at time	

Flight:

B257

KEY

Duff Data	
Minor Problems	
	OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 05/02/2007 11:34:14

Last Updated:

15/01/2007 17:55:11

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B257

Date: 15th January 2007

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TWC now operational, intermittent at high level/ low temperatures (< -45 degC)
3. CO ok
4. Flt Manager's laptop unable to connect to network
5. Nephelometer data suspect
6. Turbulence probe P0 is suspected to have frozen
7. Downward camera gain fluctuating
8. No winds on dropsonde 3 (new dropsonde – Rev F)

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls - Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B257:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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